

HORIZON 2020 - Coordination and Support Action

Grant Agreement No: 101003766

**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. 2.2

**Mapping all stakeholder activities from relevant
Polar projects including EU Polar Cluster projects**

Submission of Deliverable

Document information	
Work Package	WP 2, Stakeholder Involvement
Deliverable No	D 2.2
Deliverable title	Mapping all stakeholder activities from relevant Polar projects including EU Polar Cluster projects
Version	Final
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP - Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	UOULU (partner 3)
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – MICINN, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – ISP-CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – RCN, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – EPB, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 7 - NWO, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – DAFSHE, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – UoS-CPS, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 – UNIVIE, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 –IG-TUT, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – WOC Europe, <input type="checkbox"/> 15 – BELSPO, <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – AMAP, <input type="checkbox"/> 17 – IGOT UL, <input type="checkbox"/> 18 - SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 – UKRI-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 20 – ITU, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – USB, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 – RANNIS, <input type="checkbox"/> 23 – FAMRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 24 – ICR, <input type="checkbox"/> 25 – EPFL
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Due date	31.03.2021
Delivery date	07.04.2021

Document history	
Creation Date	
Revision	[V2]
Revision Date	18.03.2021
Author	N. Biebow, A. Strobel
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP lead approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coordinator approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Executive Board approved
Status date	30.03.2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003766

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This Deliverable summarizes the stakeholder activities and strategies planned at EU Polar Cluster projects and beyond. The input was collected in two different online surveys, the Horizon Dissemination Booster, and an open online stakeholder survey conducted by EU-PolarNet 2. The biggest groups of stakeholders identified by respondents were industry, local and regional administration, and Indigenous Communities. Most often business and administrations are engaged as experts and advisors in workshops and other events, whereas Indigenous communities are also included as equal partners and transdisciplinary research methods are used. As an overarching summary, it can be stated that there is a need and will for better coordination of stakeholder activities. The work initiated at the EU Polar Cluster stakeholder task group has good potential to collaboratively plan and conduct stakeholder activities, and also to improve transdisciplinary research methods when relevant.

1 Introduction

The Polar Regions are currently facing challenges and opportunities related to climate change, governance, globalisation and an increased economic interest. Addressing these challenges in a sustainable, equitable and just manner, aligned with the SDGs, requires joint actions and new research-based solutions. These solutions must connect innovations, new ways of thinking with existing knowledge, including local and Indigenous Knowledge. This transdisciplinary approach is conducive to the necessary holistic understanding of the socio-ecological challenges in the Polar Regions. It is important to ensure that all relevant stake- and rights holders are engaged with or represented in transdisciplinary research and innovation actions in the Polar Regions. Only truly transdisciplinary research will enable full understanding of Polar issues, and the co-production of workable solutions. Co-design and co-production of knowledge will contribute to capacity building and fostering resilient Polar communities. It will also enable industries and businesses to co-develop new technologies and activities to support Blue Growth and sustainable development in the Polar Regions.

Stakeholder involvement is an integral part of the European Polar research. It is not a novel thing but in recent years it has been understood that meaningful stakeholder involvement needs to be planned and included already in the projects' planning phase. This also calls for coordination and better understanding of stake- and rights holders, how and when they would like to be involved. EU-PolarNet 2 addresses its stakeholders in work package (WP) 2 with a designated stakeholder guardian and in cooperation within the EU Polar Cluster projects and their representatives in a stakeholder task group. This work is supported and follows the earlier work conducted in EU-PolarNet 1 and recently published first WP2 Deliverable 2.1 "Guidelines for implementing the stakeholder engagement recommendations in all transdisciplinary aspects of the EU-PolarNet 2 activities" and D 2.3 "Update of the stakeholder map developed in EU-PolarNet 1 in cooperation with the EU Polar Cluster projects", the latter is being prepared at the same time with this deliverable. These three deliverables form a guiding basis on a) how the stakeholder involvement is coordinated and conducted in just manner, and b) how transdisciplinary research methods can be improved, in both internally in EU-PolarNet 2 and jointly in EU Polar Cluster projects.

Our definition of stakeholders

Our stakeholders are those who are potentially affected by or concerned about, interested in, important to, or having any influence on the Polar research agenda or will be end-users of Polar research outcomes. Stakeholders include a wide variety of public and private sectors including policy, business, governmental and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and the wider society, including local and Indigenous peoples (right holders).

1.1 EU Polar Cluster Stakeholder task group

The EU Polar Cluster comprises currently (March 2021) 21 projects, of which 14 are Arctic projects, three Antarctic and four covering both poles. The EU Polar Cluster was formed as an EU Arctic Cluster and started the cooperation with the first initial projects in 2017. The long-lasting cooperation of these first set of EU Polar Cluster projects is clearly seen in the extensive cooperation and collaboration among these projects (Fig. 1). This cooperation has also resulted in joint workshops and sessions, policy briefings and contributions to white papers, such as “White paper on status of stakeholder engagement in Polar research”, published by EU-PolarNet 1 in 2019. The connections and cooperation between the EU Polar Cluster projects in Figure 1 are seen as a starting point for an increased cooperation and coordination of stakeholder initiatives within the projects. The connections shown in Figure 1 are not static, but during the coming years new co-operation’s and collaborations will be initiated and projects will get closer together. Projects also evolve and other forms of cooperation will be established, as an example in a form of joint education. The work started in 2017 with small set of projects has grown into a large EU Polar Cluster stakeholder task group, which will also initiate a discussion on how to improve transdisciplinary research in projects.

Figure 1. Cooperation between the EU Polar Cluster projects based on the Horizon Dissemination Booster questionnaire in late 2020 (see section 2.2). The results are based on 15 projects responses and a question on synergies with other EU Polar Cluster projects. Solid circle shows the projects with which EU-PolarNet cooperates, dashed circles other cooperation clusters. Note, the graph shows those projects that were identified by any of the 15 projects that responded to the questionnaire, and thus some connections might be missing.

In the centre of Figure 1 is EU-PolarNet, which has a role as initiator of cooperation and coordination within the EU Polar Cluster, EU-PolarNet also listed more synergies with other projects than any other project. The project PROTECT is one of the most recently initiated projects, which has not yet built the connections nor planned its stakeholder activities, therefore appears outside the circles. During the coming years it is anticipated that PROTECT will also move closer to other projects as cooperation is established when seen to be meaningful.

2 Main Objectives

The overall objective of Stakeholder involvement (WP2) is to develop strategies for capacity building related to meaningful stakeholder involvement in polar research and to sustain this expertise in a

Stakeholder Involvement Tool to be developed as part of the European Polar Coordination Office, the legacy of EU-PolarNet 2 after the end of the project. This deliverable and the information gathered serves as a starting point of better coordination of stakeholder activities and improving transdisciplinary research methods both in EU-PolarNet 2 and its WPs and in all EU Polar Cluster projects.

Collecting input on stakeholder activities conducted in European Polar research, particularly in EU Polar Cluster projects, but also beyond, gives an initial understanding on how polar projects can increase their cooperation and collaboration. How these could be better coordinated and planned further in EU Polar Cluster stakeholder task group will be discussed with the entire task group.

2.1 Mapping the stakeholder activities in polar research projects

The first aim of this deliverable is to map on-going and planned stake- and rights holder engagement activities in European polar projects and beyond. This mapping is mainly based on an EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey conducted in February 2021. The survey included specific questions on target stakeholder groups and strategies for their involvement. The four stakeholder strategies used are the ones identified during first EU-PolarNet and in the White paper on the status on stakeholder activities in polar research: equal partners, advisors, experts, and visitors.

This mapping and identification of stakeholder groups is also highly relevant for EU-PolarNet 2 and the work conducted in other WPs. It supports the engagement of all the relevant stakeholders in prioritising European Polar Research, which is also supported by the recent Deliverable 2.1 with guidelines on stakeholder involvement in all EU-PolarNet 2 activities and an updated stakeholder map (D2.3) being developed at the moment.

2.2 Better coordination of polar stakeholder activities

Good and efficient coordination of joint stakeholder activities is a key for avoiding stakeholder fatigue and for a better use of resources of all EU Polar Cluster projects. By mapping the planned activities, the linkages between the research projects are found and new cooperation and collaboration can be built. Stakeholder activities should not be only looked from the researchers' perspective but also from the stakeholder's perspective: does research provide any benefits or is it meaningful for them? A good

relationship between researchers and stake- and rights holders should be based on mutual respect and this can be gained by ensuring that relationships that have already been established between researchers/research projects are respected and that new (research) activities will not interfere or negatively influence these relationships. In the EU Polar Cluster, the stakeholder task group aims for this also by also improving transdisciplinary research methods and the information received for this deliverable will be taken into practice by this group.

The second aim of this deliverable is therefore to develop better coordination on engaging with stake- and right holders in the EU Polar Cluster projects and beyond. This would also lead into a better coordination and developing joint actions to avoid duplication and stakeholder fatigue.

The results presented here are based on two online surveys: the Horizon Dissemination Booster questionnaire which was open in late 2020 and the EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey (Annex 1, 2) which was open in February 2021. The Horizon Dissemination Booster was open only to EU Polar Cluster projects and thus all fifteen answers were given by those projects. The EU-PolarNet 2 open online *“Survey on on-going and planned stakeholder and right-holder engagement in European Polar Research”* (see appendix 1 and 2) was open to anyone and was sent to EU Polar Cluster projects and in addition shared in the EU-PolarNet 2 newsletter, website and social media, news and/or email lists of European Polar Board, University of the Arctic, SCAR, Polar Prediction Project Societal and Economic Research Application (PPP-SERA), and European Space Agency Polar Science Cluster projects (Arctic projects funded by science for society and Antarctic/global project support to science element). The Horizon Dissemination Booster focused on projects’ results and how those would be used by stakeholders. The EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey focused on stakeholder groups that will be involved and how they are engaged during the project’s lifetime, thus two questionnaires are complementary and in many cases the results presented are only based on either one.

3 Stakeholder activities in Polar research projects

Fifteen EU Polar Cluster projects responded to the Horizon Dissemination Booster online questionnaire, and 21 individual answers were submitted to the EU-PolarNet 2 online survey on stakeholder involvement. There were nine EU Polar Cluster projects that responded to both the Horizon Dissemination Booster questionnaire and the EU-PolarNet 2 survey. In case of the survey, there was one project that had submitted three separate answers. Therefore, when taking all this into

account, there the responses of 25 separate projects or individual researchers or organisations were included in this deliverable.

The number of Arctic projects was clearly highest (Figure 2) with 19 projects compared to three Antarctic and three bipolar projects, which is also in line with dominance of Arctic projects in the EU Polar Cluster. It can also be seen as an indication that the stakeholder involvement is integral part in the Arctic, which is an inhabited region with cities and communities. In addition to the EU Polar Cluster projects, three ESA Polar Science Cluster projects responded to the online stakeholder survey (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The division of Arctic, Antarctic and polar projects, individual researcher and organisations funded by European Commission (EU Polar Cluster), European Space Agency (ESA) and other, which answered either to Horizon Dissemination Booster or online stakeholder survey. The EU Polar Cluster projects that answered to both surveys have been summarized to avoid doubling the number of replies.

3.1 Main stakeholders and strategies used for stakeholder involvement

The main stakeholder target group identified as the user of the EU Polar Cluster projects' research results in the Horizon Dissemination Booster questionnaire was clearly the academia and researchers: 80% as first target group and 66% as their second stakeholder target group. This indicates that most

polar projects do not see how society in general, industry or communities could benefit from their research results and research results are only seen as interest of academia and science community.

When stakeholder involvement was asked from the point of view of initiating or on-going projects, the results were quite different. In the EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey, the main stakeholder groups identified represented industry, local and regional administration, and Indigenous communities (Figure 3). In case of local and Indigenous communities, particularly reindeer herding in Nordic countries by Sámi and fishing was mentioned. In case of industry: mining, fisheries and tourism were the main topics. All these are relevant to Arctic societies and regional development as well as policies, which also shows the dominance of Arctic projects (see Annex 3 for full list of stakeholders given).

Figure 3. Target stakeholder groups identified in the EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey listed by each respondent (% of all multiple answers by each respondents [number of answers]). The category “other” consists of seven cases of academic and researchers, rest vary from local communities to European Commission.

The respondents to the EU-PolarNet 2 online survey included also non EU Polar Cluster projects. There was, however, no difference in between the EU Polar Cluster projects and other projects in case of main stakeholder groups. What was notable is that most extensive stakeholder initiatives in EU Polar Cluster projects, with several different groups, are planned and will be conducted in Arctic and Polar projects that have started their projects in 2020: CHARTER, ECOTIP, FACE-IT and JUSTNORTH. One way of describing these projects is that they represent the new generation of Arctic and Polar research

where stakeholders are an integral part of their actions from project partners to experts (Fig. 4). What this also indicates is that European Commission has succeeded in including societal relevance into their latest H2020 funding calls. Interestingly though the strategies used for stakeholder involvement have not changed within EU Polar Cluster projects starting in before 2020 and those that started in 2020. The most used strategies for stakeholder engagement are either advisors or experts, in case of Indigenous communities and organisations they are included as often equal partners, experts and advisors (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The strategies used for different stakeholder groups, answers represent both EU Polar Cluster and other projects, individual researchers and organisation that answered to the online stakeholder survey. The group “other” includes mostly research and academia, local people, European Commission and Reindeer herding cooperatives.

Two specific Antarctic projects responded to the EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey, one represented an EU Polar Cluster project and the other one not. The answers point towards the same finding, which we previously identified in EU-PolarNet 1 in collecting responses on the “White paper on status of stakeholder engagement in polar research”: stakeholder involvement does not play a

major role in Antarctic projects. One Antarctic project noted that they do not have plans for stakeholder engagement, whereas the non EU Polar Cluster project led by Australian Antarctic research involves both business (Tasmanian Polar network) and local Australian and New Zealand's regional administrations. What should be highlighted here is that throughout the planning and initiating of the stakeholder activities in EU-PolarNet 1 and 2, the Antarctic has been specifically targeted and project partners have made efforts to ensure that Antarctic is included. However, the responses to these requests have been very scarce, which can be an indication of many things. However, it also shows that stakeholder involvement or transdisciplinary research are not seen as an integral part of the research in Antarctic. This is particularly clear for Europe also as due to its geographical location, there are no Antarctic gateway cities, such as those in Australia and New Zealand mentioned also in this EU-PolarNet 2 online survey.

3.2 Types of stakeholder activities

Mostly used stakeholder strategies identified in the online survey were advisors and experts and this can also be seen in mostly used forms of the stakeholder activities (Figure 5), which are workshops, sessions in conjunction of Polar conferences or standalone seminars. The category "other" includes interviews, which covers most of the answers under "other" and thus can be stated as one of the popular ways of engaging with stakeholders. Online survey and questionnaire remain to be an easy way to target large group of stakeholders at the same time in a relatively easy and quick way.

Figure 5. Different types of stakeholder activities identified in online stakeholder survey. The category “other” includes mostly interviews, either one by one or in small groups. Note that this category also includes answers “no activity is planned”.

The EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey also asked for the formats of possible cooperation in stakeholder activities and joint workshops, joint sessions and presentations were particularly mentioned, but also joint policy statements to the European Commission, Arctic Council and its working groups. Some of the responses were specific targeting to certain projects such as better coordination of icebreaker operations. Importantly also the joint online education was listed and co-produced study plans and collaboration with communities. Latter ones are also important for capacity building.

3.3 Cooperation between the EU Polar Cluster projects and beyond

In addition to getting information on planned stakeholder involvement and strategies for those, both the Horizon Dissemination Booster and the EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey provided a good basis for continuing the existing cooperation and information to build concrete ideas for initiating new cooperation and methods for transdisciplinary research. Integral tool for cooperation between the projects is the EU Polar Cluster and its stakeholder task group, which is co-chaired by EU-PolarNet 2 WP2 leader and the stakeholder guardian. This will make sure that all information gathered for this deliverable will be used in planning and initiating joint activities to avoid duplication and stakeholder fatigue. It is notable that the projects in EU Polar Cluster are different and their needs for cooperation are different, thus there is no “one stop shop” that works for all. By working together best practices and ways of cooperation are formulated and three WP2 deliverables mentioned earlier (D2.1, D2.3 and this one) feed into this planning and processes. Within EU-PolarNet 2, the stakeholder guardian will make sure that, whenever relevant, this information will be used for the benefit of whole EU-PolarNet 2 project and its other WPs.

The EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey received also answers from non-EU-Polar Cluster projects, which gives European polar research also an excellent opportunity to cooperate beyond Europe as responses were given by individual researchers, projects and organisations representing, in addition to Europe, United States of America, the Russian Federation and Australia. Cooperation. Collaboration and coordination are three key elements also in stakeholder involvement; this is seen as a cooperation and collaboration between the polar research projects but also with the polar, Arctic or Antarctic science organisations and other organisations and networks. By creating synergies and links with the coordination, stakeholders can be involved in the issues that are relevant to them in an equitable manner and in their own terms.

Acknowledgements

All respondents, EU Polar Cluster projects and other contributors from Europe, USA, Russian Federation and Australia, are thanked for their valuable contributions in allocating time to answer the EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey. The Horizon Dissemination Booster provided also important information and EU Polar Cluster projects who responded to its questionnaire are thanked for the equally important input.

4 Annexes

Annex 1 Invitation to take part to the online survey

Annex 2 Online survey form

Annex 3 List of stakeholder groups identified in EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey

Annex 1: Invitation to take part to the online survey

Invitation to take part to online survey on stake- and rightholder engagement conducted in European Polar research projects

We invite European Polar research projects to take part to this **online survey on on-going and planned stakeholder and right holder engagement in European Polar Research** (Arctic and Antarctic). The survey is open until **February 28th, 2021**. This survey is an integral part of the EU-PolarNet 2 project and aims to support an effective stakeholder engagement process feeding into the prioritisation of European Polar research. A second aim is to increase cooperation between the Polar research projects in the EU Polar Cluster coordinated by EU-PolarNet 2, but we hope to expand our cooperation beyond this cluster as well.

What information is gathered in this survey?

- Ongoing and planned stakeholder and rightholder engagement activities in European Arctic and Antarctic projects. This survey welcomes contributions from all projects working at Polar regions.
- Information for the update of the stakeholder map, developed in EU-PolarNet 1, including intermediaries.

How do your stake- and rightholders benefit from participation to this survey?

- A better coordination on engaging with stake- and rightholders in the [EU Polar Cluster](#) projects and beyond. This would lead into a better coordination and developing joint actions to avoid duplication and stakeholder fatigue.
- A respectful relationship between researchers and stake- and rightholders based on mutual respect. This is gained by ensuring that relationships that have already been established between researchers/research projects are respected and that new (research) activities will not interfere or negatively influence these relationships.
- To make sure that all the relevant stakeholders are engaged in prioritising European Polar Research actions.

How do we use the results?

- The results of the survey will be compiled into two public EU-PolarNet 2 public deliverables on first updating the stakeholder map and secondly on mapping the stakeholder activities. Both are EU-

PolarNet 2 WP2 Stakeholder Involvement deliverables responsible by University of Oulu (UOULU), Finland (WP leader) and Netherlands Polar Programme under Dutch Research Council, Netherlands (NWO).

What is our definition of stakeholders?

- Our stakeholders are those who are potentially affected by or concerned about, interested in, important to, or having any influence on the Polar research agenda or will be end-users of Polar research outcomes. Stakeholders include a wide variety of public and private sectors including policy, business, governmental and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and the wider society, including local and Indigenous peoples (right holders).

What is EU-PolarNet 2?

EU-PolarNet 2, Coordinating and Co-designing European research area, is a project (2020-24) funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 framework programme under grant agreement No 101003766. It is a European network of 25 partners to co-develop and advance European Polar Research actions and to give evidence-based advice to policymaking processes.

The ambition of EU-PolarNet 2 is to establish a sustainable and inclusive platform to co-develop and advance European Polar research actions and to give evidence-based advice to policymaking processes. This platform will allow to further develop the coordination of Polar research actions in Europe and with overseas partners. By involving all relevant stake- and rightholders it will support the development of transdisciplinary and transnational Polar research actions of high societal relevance.

More information: <https://eu-polarnet.eu/>

Thank you for your collaboration!

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us:

EU-PolarNet 2 Stakeholder Engagement leader Dr. Kirsi Latola, kirsi.latola@oulu.fi

EU-PolarNet 2 Stakeholder Guardian Dr. Annette Scheepstra, a.j.m.scheepstra@rug.nl

Annex 2: Online survey form

Survey on stake- and right-holder engagement conducted in European Polar research and coordination projects

This survey has been created by [EU-PolarNet 2](#), Coordinating and Co-designing European research area project (2020-24) funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 framework programme under grant agreement No 101003766.

This survey continues and builds on the work conducted during the first EU-PolarNet 1 project in 2015-20 during which a [White Paper on status of stakeholder engagement in Polar research](#) was written in a collaboration with other Polar projects.

The aim of this survey is twofold. First it aims to collect information on stake- and right-holder engagement in both Arctic and Antarctic projects for better coordination and developing joint actions to avoid duplication and stakeholder fatigue. Secondly it aims to update the stakeholder map, developed in EU-PolarNet 1, for making sure that all the relevant stakeholders are engaged in prioritising European Polar Research.

The results of the survey will be compiled into two EU-PolarNet 2 public deliverables on first updating the stakeholder map and secondly on mapping the stakeholder activities. Both are EU-PolarNet 2 WP2 Stakeholder Involvement deliverables responsible by University of Oulu (UOULU), Finland (WP leader) and Netherlands Polar Programme under Dutch Research Council, Netherlands (NWO).

Please answer to the survey by February 28th, 2021.

Thank you for your collaboration!

If you have any questions, please don't hesitate to contact us:

- WP2 leader Dr. Kirsi Latola, kirsi.latola@oulu.fi
- EU-PolarNet 2 Stakeholder Guardian Dr. Annette Scheepstra, a.j.m.scheepstra@rug.nl

This survey forms part of the EU project EU-PolarNet 2, thus processing and sharing of personal data comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation ("GDPR")).

1. Are you answering on behalf of [EU Polar Cluster](#) project? *

- Yes, please add the name of the EU-Polar Cluster project:
- No

2. If you don't represent an EU Polar Cluster project, please tell us what kind of project you are representing (e.g. name and type of project, funding

5. Which stakeholder engagement strategies you use (see diagram below)? You can choose several strategies

Time needed for the stakeholder engagement with local and Indigenous communities during the project

- Equal partners
- Advisors
- Experts
- Visitors

6. What are your main stakeholder groups? *

Please indicate which are your main stakeholders, you can choose as many needed. Please give the name of the specific stakeholder e.g. which city, company, county, NGO, media, organisation or operator, thank you!

- Industry, please specify
- Business (SMEs etc), please specify
- Local administration (cities, municipalities.), please specify
- Regional administration (counties etc), please specify
- Chambers of commerce or similar, please specify
- NGOs, please specify
- Media, please specify
- Indigenous communities and/or organisations, please specify
- Tourism operator, either regional, national or international, please specify
- Other, please specify

7. What strategies (listed in question 5) you use for each of your main stakeholder groups?

	Equal partners	Advisors	Experts	Visitors
Industry	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Business	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Local administration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regional administration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Chambers of commerce or similar	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
NGOs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Media	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Indigenous communities and/or organisations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tourism operator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, what <input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

8. What stakeholder activities will you conduct during 2021-2023? *

- Online surveys/questionnaires
- Sessions in conjunction with Polar Congresses
- Other, please specify
- Public workshops
- Public hearings
- Stand alone seminars

15. Contact information in case you would like receive the public deliverables or build cooperation. Note that contact information or personal details will not be published and are not shared further.

First name	<input type="text"/>
Last name	<input type="text"/>
Email	<input type="text"/>
Organisation	<input type="text"/>

16. I consent that the information I have given above can be used for EU-PolarNet 2 Deliverables D2.2 Mapping all stakeholder activities from relevant Polar projects including EU Polar Cluster projects and D2.3 Update of the stakeholder map developed in EU-PolarNet 1 in cooperation with the EU Polar Cluster projects. *

- Yes
 No

Annex 3: List of stakeholder groups identified in EU-PolarNet 2 online stakeholder survey

Stakeholder group	Stakeholder identified
Tourism operator, either regional, national or international	Ponant, Oceanwide marine expeditions
Tourism operator, either regional, national or international	Arctic tour operators organizations and national/regional tourism organizations
Tourism operator, either regional, national or international	only local
Tourism operator, either regional, national or international	reindeer tourism enterprises in northern Fennoscandia
Media	circumarctic and local
Media	regional newspapers, TV channels (additionally, web presence, twitter posts)
Regional administration (counties etc)	Greenland Self-Government
Regional administration (counties etc)	Region Västerbotten Turism
Regional administration (counties etc)	USA
Regional administration (counties etc)	Australian and New Zealand Governments
Regional administration (counties etc)	as related to study sites
Regional administration (counties etc)	regional administrations in SWE, FIN, RUS
Regional administration (counties etc)	northern Norway, northern Sweden, northern Finland, northwestern Russia

Regional administration (counties etc)	Sakha (Yakutia) republic regional administration
Local administration (cities, municipalities..),	possibly 2-3 Greenlandic municipalities
Local administration (cities, municipalities..)	Svalbard governor
Local administration (cities, municipalities..)	local authorities and organizations at study sites, e.g municipalities, livelihood organizations
Local administration (cities, municipalities..),	cities and municipalities in SWE, FIN, RUS
Local administration (cities, municipalities..)	various, across regions
Local administration (cities, municipalities..),	Local administrations of municipalities of Sakha (Yakutia) republic, Russia - Nizhnekolymsky district, Olekminsky district, Anabar district, Neryungrinsky district, Oymyakonsky district, Ust-Maysky district
Local administration (cities, municipalities..)	Hunters and Trappers Committees, Municipalities
Industry	Fishing sector in Greenland
Industry	Fishing industry
Industry	climate service end users
Industry	Swedish Lapland Visitor Board
Industry	Maritime industry: ARCTIA, TOTAL, Ficantieri, SINTEF, Northern Shipping company
Industry	fisheries, tourism
Industry	energy, mining, tourism
Industry	occasional consultations with mining/gas/oil companies, forestry
Indigenous communities and/or organisations	2-3 fishing communities. cooperation yet to be explored
Indigenous communities and/or organisations	Arctic stakeholder communities
Indigenous communities and/or organisations	Saami reindeer herding communities

Indigenous communities and/or organisations	at study sites and via international organizations
Indigenous communities and/or organisations	indigenous organisations in SWE, FIN, RUS
Indigenous communities and/or organisations	Sámi, Nenets, and Izhma-Komi communities
Indigenous communities and/or organisations	Indigenous tribal communities in the case study districts of Sakha (Yakutia) republic
Indigenous communities and/or organisations	Several local communities (Aklavik, Tuktoyaktuk, Inuvik, Tiski, Longyearbyen, Ilulissat, etc.)
Business (SMEs etc)	research, University of South Bohemia
Business (SMEs etc)	climate service end users
Business (SMEs etc)	Tasmanian Polar Network
Business (SMEs etc)	as related to tourism and fisheries
Business (SMEs etc)	local tourism business, reindeer herding, fishing
Business (SMEs etc)	reindeer-herding enterprises and other companies involved in renewable resource use
Other	Greenland Survey as intermediary (full list of users not ready yet)
Other	Well, in deep sea biology there are few stakeholders besides fishing/mining industry.
Other	no scheduled stakeholder interaction yet
Other	scientific community, operators of research vessels,
Other	Academia
Other	Academia
Other	Polar scientific community
Other	Scientific Research Organisations
Other	EU DGs, international scientific assessments; Arctic Council; research coordinator, international scientific organizations focusing on the Arctic; early career scientists; national government authorities in Norway and Greenland as relevant to management of fjord systems
Other	reindeer herding cooperatives

Other	Science community
Other	local people living in the research communities
NGOs	agencies with relevant interests, e.g. conservation
NGOs	ThirdWay
NGOs	relevant environmental NGO (national and international)
NGOs	indigenous, environmental
NGOs	local organisations in the sphere of public welfare, possibly environmental protection